

Some Physico-Chemical Studies on a Protein-Rich Fruit Seed (*Aegle marmelos*-Correa)

N. BANERJI* and M. MAITI

Indian Institute of Experimental Medicine,
Calcutta-700 032, India

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THE tree, *Aegle marmelos* is found wild in Sub-Himalayan tracts, in central and south India and in Burma. The fruit is regarded as astringent, digestive and stomachic. It is also used in diarrhoea and dysentery¹. The seed oil is reported to have purgative value². In the present communication, chemical composition and sodium dodecyl sulphate-polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis (SDS-PAGE) studies on different protein fractions of protein-rich seed kernel are described. This is the first time to report such a high-protein content of a fruit seed.

Materials and Methods :

Isolation of materials : The seeds were collected from the ripe fruits of the plant (*Aegle marmelos*) grown in West Bengal, India. Dried powdered seed kernel (10 g) was extracted with chloroform-methanol (3 : 1) at room temperature for 12 hr. The slurry was filtered, the residue was dried to yield defatted fraction (6.8 g approx.). From the filtrate the chloroform-methanol was evaporated off to yield the seed oil fractions (3.2 g approx.). The defatted material was extracted with water at room temperature and filtered. The filtrate was reduced to a smaller volume and the water soluble fraction was precipitated with ethanol. The yield of this fraction was 2 to 3% of the defatted fraction.

Analytical methods : Protein was estimated by the method of Lowry *et al*³ by using bovine serum albumin (Sigma Chemical) as standard and also the protein-nitrogen was estimated by micro-Kjeldahl method. SDS-polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis (7.5%) was carried out following in general the method of Weber and Osborn⁴, the gel system was calibrated using the following standard proteins : bovine serum albumin (67000), ovalbumin (43000), chymotrypsinogen (25000), myoglobin (17800) and cytochrome C (12400). For preparation of the sample, 10 mg of the seed fraction was added to 5 ml of 0.01 M sodium phosphate buffer (pH 7.2) containing 1% SDS and 1% β -mercaptoethanol. The mixture was heated at 100° for 3 min and then 20-25 μ l of the mixture with 20% sucrose and 0.003% bromophenol blue applied to the gel.

The fatty acid content of the seed oil was estimated by the method of Haskins⁵. The fatty acids mixtures on treatment with ethereal diazomethane

yielded the methyl esters of fatty acids. Gas liquid chromatographic (GLC) analysis of these methyl esters were carried out with a Hewlett Packard Model 5730A gas chromatograph fitted with a FID detector. Nitrogen was used as carrier gas. A 6' $\times$ $\frac{1}{4}$ " OD column containing 10% Apiezone on chromosorb WHP was used for the detection of fatty acids. The analysis was carried out against a standard mixture of fatty acids methyl esters.

Total carbohydrate was estimated by the method of Dubois *et al*⁶, using D-glucose as standard. The following solvents were used for descending paper chromatography of sugars : (a) ethylacetate-pyridine-water (8 : 2 : 1); (b) *n*-butanol-pyridine-water (6 : 4 : 3). Whatman No 1 chromatography paper was used. Spray reagents were : (i) saturated solution of aniline oxalate in water and (ii) aniline hydrogen phthalate.

Results and Discussion

Chemical analysis revealed that the seed contained 62% protein (water soluble 2% and 60%, insoluble), 32% oil, 3% carbohydrate and 3% ash. The figures presented were the average of four independent estimations. The percentage of protein content of the seed was found to be the same by application of both Lowry *et al*³ and Kjeldahl methods. The remarkably high protein content was found to be 32 to 42% in soyabean (*Glycine max*, L), whereas this seed contains 62% protein.

SDS-PAGE (Fig. 1a) of the defatted seed preparation gives 7 bands of respective MWS 110000, 106000, 80000, 60000, 36000, 20000 and 14500 daltons, which may be due to either seven different proteins or different subunits of some protein(s). Of these, only three components comprised the major fractions of the seed proteins. It was interesting to note that the water-soluble fraction (2-3% of defatted seed which contained 95% protein) revealed only single band of average MW 18000 daltons (Fig. 1b). Evidence of the single band was also confirmed by applying more than 100 μ g of the sample per gel under identical conditions (Fig. 1c). This single protein band clearly indicated the presence of one subunit. This fraction on hydrolysis with N-H₂SO₄ yielded D-galactose, L-arabinose and D-xylose. Further studies are under progress to find out whether this protein fraction is a glycoprotein or a single polypeptide chain containing more than one subunit or it is a mechanical mixture of protein and polysaccharide. Amino acids composition of this protein is also under study. The hydrolysate of whole seed kernel was also found to contain the same sugars. As mentioned previously the seed oil was found to be 32% in which 28% was fatty acids. The fatty acid of the total seed oil were identified as palmitic acid,

* Address for correspondence : Indian Institute of Experimental Medicine, Calcutta-700 032, India.

Fig. 1. SDS-polyacrilamide gel electrophoresis pattern of: defatted seed protein fraction, 50 μ g (a); and water-soluble fraction of defatted seed, 15 μ g (b) and 100 μ g (c).

stearic acid, oleic acid, linoleic acid and linolenic acid using GLC by converting them into their respective methyl-esters. The non-fatty acid fraction isolated from this was found to contain β -sitosterol (m.p. 137-38° and $[\alpha]_D^{25} - 35^\circ$) and an unidentified compound. The seed oil is reported to have some purgative effect² which needs some pharmacological studies. Considering all the above mentioned remarkable characteristics of the seed kernel, further studies on it are in progress.

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Heterocyclic Systems, Part I. Reactions of 2, 3-Dichloroquinoxaline with Cyclic Thioureas, Dithiocarbamates and Thioamides

VIJAY K. CHADHA* and V. K. SAXENA

Department of Chemistry, Government Post-graduate College, Churu-331 001 (Rajasthan)

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IN continuation to our earlier work^{1,2}, now syntheses of II, III, IV and V have been accomplished. I when condensed with 2-thiobarbituric acid in absolute alcohol yielded II, whereas with 4-methyl-2-mercapto imidazoline furnished III. Since 4-methyl-2-mercapto imidazoline is an unsymmetrical thiourea it is likely to yield 2-methyl-2,3-dihydro imidazo[2',1':2,3]thiazolo[4,5-b]quinoxaline(III) or its 3-methyl isomer. However since only one compound was obtained (TLC), it has been assigned the structure (III) on analogy with our earlier work³, but needs confirmation. Thiazolo-quinoxalines (IV) and (V) were synthesized by the reactions of I with substituted ammonium dithiocarbamates and thioamides in presence of fused sodium acetate in absolute ethanol. Structures II, III, IV and V have been characterized by IR spectra (*vide experimental*).

1. 2-Thiobarbituric Acid, EtOH;
2. 4-Methyl-2-mercapto-imidazoline, EtOH;
3. RNECBSNH₄, EtOH, NaOAc;
4. RCSNH₂, EtOH, NaOAc.

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected. IR spectra were taken in Nujol mull. TLC was performed on silicagel plates using acetone-benzene (1:3) as solvent system.

3H-Pyrimidino[2',1':2,3]thiazolo [4,5-b]quinoxaline-2,4-dione (II):

A solution of I (1.00 g, 0.005 mole) and 2-thiobarbituric acid (0.72 g, 0.005 mole) in anhydrous

* For correspondence.